

Microwave-assisted solvent-free synthesis of some bio-active substituted dihalo 1,4-benzoquinones on silica gel solid support[†]

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Abstract : An environmentally benign solvent-free microwave-assisted synthesis of biologically active 2,5-diarylamino-3,6-dihalo-1,4-benzoquinones by the condensation of substituted anilines and chloranil has been reported on the inorganic solid support of silica gel.

Keywords : Microwave irradiation, solvent-free synthesis, silica gel solid support, dihalo 1,4-benzoquinones.

Introduction

The increasing need to provide highly pure small molecules as potential modulators of therapeutic targets is driving the development of novel synthetic technologies that can produce compounds at very high rate¹. Microwave-assisted organic chemistry is a relatively new technology that has been shown to significantly improve productivity in the generation of combinatorial libraries and complex target molecules^{1,2}. In recent years, microwave irradiation (MWI) has been demonstrated not only to dramatically accelerate many organic reactions, but also to improve yields and selectivity. The impact of microwave-assisted organic synthesis on drug discovery is just beginning to be realised³, but it is clearly evident in the rapid increase in the number of published articles focusing on the use of this technology to drive the discovery and optimisation of new leads⁴.

The coupling of MWI with the use of inorganic supported reagents, under solvent-free conditions, provides a chemical process having special advantages such as enhanced reaction rates, higher yields, ease of manipulation, the opportunity to work with open vessels and finally the possibility to upscale the reaction to multi-gram amounts⁵. Work-up procedures are considerably simplified, as in many cases; the pure product can be obtained directly from the crude reaction mixture by simple extraction, distillation or sublimation. In addition solvent-

free organic reactions make synthesis simpler, save energy, and prevent solvent wastes, hazards and toxicity⁶.

1,4-Benzoquinones are found in animal and plant cells and they play prominent role in cellular respiration processes like bioenergetics transport agents, oxidative phosphorylation and electron transfer⁷. *p*-Benzoquinones derivatives are of current interest due to their association with wide spectrum biological and pharmacological activity⁸. Benzoquinone derivatives containing "3,6-dichloro-1,4-benzoquinone" moiety exhibit potent antibacterial⁹, antifungal¹⁰, antimalarial¹¹, antiviral¹², pesticidal¹³ and anticancer¹⁴ activities. A variety of substituted dianilide 1,4-benzoquinones, synthesised in our laboratory, have also been reported to possess antitumour activity¹⁵. The most important application of functionalised dihalo 1,4-benzoquinones, in the field of medicinal chemistry, lies in their use as potential synthetic building blocks for the synthesis of novel N-, O- and/or S-containing heterocyclic drug candidates¹⁶. Substituted 1,4-benzoquinones are also used as catalyst¹⁷, intermediate¹⁸, ligand¹⁹, analyte²⁰ and monomer²¹ in various industrial processes of commercial importance. In the field of dye industry, the dianilide 1,4-benzoquinones are used as starting molecule for the commercial production of direct and reactive triphenodioxazine (TPDO) dye²².

Though many synthetic strategies²³⁻²⁷ have been reported for the preparation of dihalo 1,4-benzoquinone

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

derivatives, most of them include use of expensive, commercially non-available or hazardous reagents, drastic reaction conditions, longer reaction time and cumbersome work-up procedure. The use of silica gel solid support in organic synthetic protocol, especially when coupled with MWI, not only reduce the reaction time and enhance the yield considerably, but also eliminates the requirement of catalyst and solvent from reaction step thus simplify the work-up procedures²⁸. An appreciable amount of solvent is still required for adsorption of reagents in the solid supports and elution of the products.

In this paper, some novel bio-active 2,5-diaryl-amino-3,6-dichloro-1,4-benzoquinones, are synthesised under solvent-free conditions on the solid support of silica gel from monosubstituted anilines and 2,3,4,5-tetrachloro-1,4-benzoquinones (chloranil) using microwave technology.

Results and discussion

2,5-Diaryl-amino-3,6-dichloro-1,4-benzoquinone derivatives **3** were prepared by the condensation of monosubstituted aryl amine **1a-i** with 2,3,4,5-tetrachloro-1,4-benzoquinone **2** on the inorganic solid support of silica gel under microwave irradiation (Scheme 1). The same synthesis has been reported earlier under conventional conditions by using anhydrous sodium acetate as base (Scheme 1)²⁹. But the use of silica gel under solvent-free

fits of this protocol are, such as, safety is largely increased, work-up is considerably simplified, cost is reduced, increased amount of reactants can be used, and reactivity is enhanced without dilution. All these factors are important in industry.

The condensation of 2 mmol monosubstituted aryl amine **1a-i** and 1 mmol chloranil **2**, using silica gel as solid support under microwave irradiations, gave 2,5-diaryl-amino-3,6-dichloro-1,4-benzoquinones **3a-i**. The reaction took 45–90 s for completion affording 87–94% yield (Table 1). The use of silica gel as an inorganic solid support not only eliminates the use of external bases for catalyzing the reaction but also avoids the use of organic solvents. Only a limited amount of EtOH was used for adsorbing the reactants on the solid support. Silica gel mediated organic synthesis is proved efficient in terms of reaction time, yield, elimination of organic solvents and external bases.

The same reaction took 6 h accompanied by 60–86% yield in conventional methods (Table 1). On replacement of silica gel with other solid supports, such as acidic, neutral and basic alumina, it was found that no reaction occurred and reactants remain unchanged.

Scheme 1

conditions makes the reaction more efficient than its solution counterpart, since molecules in a crystal are arranged tightly and regularly. Furthermore, by eliminating organic solvent during the synthesis leads to a clean and economical synthetic protocol. Other tangible bene-

The structures of the synthesized 2,5-diaryl-amino-3,6-dichloro-1,4-benzoquinones **3a-i** were confirmed from physico-analytical (Table 2) and spectral data (Table 3). The % element found for CHN elements are in close agreement with their calculated values (Table 2). The UV

Table 1. Comparison of reaction time and yield of the compounds **3a-i**

Compd.	Reaction time		Yield (%)	
	Solid supported microwave (s)	Solution phase conventional (h)	Solid supported microwave	Solution phase conventional
3a	45	6	92	75
3b	90	6	93	60
3c	90	6	89	65
3d	45	6	91	62
3e	75	6	87	70
3f	80	6	88	86
3g	90	6	90	75
3h	50	6	94	75
3i	72	6	90	80

Table 2. Physical and analytical data of the compounds **3a-i**

Compd.	Molecular formula	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)		
			C	H	N
3a	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	248	60.16 (60.13)	3.34 (3.31)	7.79 (7.72)
3b	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ F ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	318	54.71 (54.70)	2.55 (2.52)	7.08 (7.05)
3c	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	198	61.97 (61.92)	4.16 (4.12)	7.19 (7.16)
3d	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄	283	57.29 (57.26)	3.84 (3.81)	6.68 (6.65)
3e	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ F ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	260	54.71 (54.69)	2.55 (2.54)	7.08 (7.04)
3f	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₂	350	50.46 (50.42)	2.33 (2.31)	6.54 (6.49)
3g	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	225	41.77 (41.70)	1.93 (1.90)	5.41 (5.36)
3h	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	275	61.97 (61.94)	4.16 (4.14)	7.19 (7.17)
3i	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄	240	57.29 (57.25)	3.84 (3.81)	6.68 (6.65)

Table 3. Spectral data of the compounds **3a-i**

Compd.	UV	IR (KBr)	¹ H NMR	¹³ C NMR	FAB MS
	λ_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)	DMSO (δ)	DMSO (δ)	<i>m/z</i> (% , fragment)
3a	388	3239 (NH) 1651 (CO)	7.12–7.40 (10H, m, Ar-H) 8.30 (2H, s, NH, D ₂ O ex.)	172.9 (CO)	359 (30%, M ⁺) 361 (16%, M ⁺ + 2) 329 (25%, M ⁺ - 2NH)
3b	360	3240 (NH) 1656 (CO)	7.21–7.64 (8H, m, Ar-H) 8.28 (2H, s, NH, D ₂ O ex.)	171.2 (CO)	395 (48%, M ⁺) 397 (16%, M ⁺ + 2) 361 (17%, M ⁺ - 2F)

Table-3 (contd.)

3c	367.2	3242 (NH)	2.28 (6H, s, 2CH ₃)	17.6 (CH ₃)	387 (100%, M ⁺)
		1652 (CO)	7.08–7.26 (8H, m, Ar-H) 8.20 (2H, s, NH, D ₂ O ex.)	172.5 (CO)	389 (33%, M ⁺ + 2) 351 (35%, M ⁺ - HCl)
3d	390	3240 (NH)	3.87 (6H, s, 2OCH ₃)	55.9 (OCH ₃)	419 (100%, M ⁺)
		1660 (CO)	6.90–7.24 (8H, m, Ar-H) 8.24 (2H, s, NH, D ₂ O ex.)	172.8 (CO)	421 (33%, M ⁺ + 2) 388 (25%, M ⁺ - OCH ₃) 357 (38%, M ⁺ - 2OCH ₃)
3e	390	3239 (NH)	7.13–7.20 (8H, m, Ar-H)	170.8 (CO)	395 (63%, M ⁺)
		1651 (CO)	8.33 (2H, s, NH, D ₂ O ex.)		394 (45%, M ⁺ - 1) 365 (15%, M ⁺ - 2NH) 361 (56%, M ⁺ - 2F)
3f	385	3230 (NH)	7.03–7.53 (8H, m, Ar-H)	170.2 (CO)	428 (77%, M ⁺)
		1650 (CO)	8.26 (2H, s, NH, D ₂ O ex.)		430 (100%, M ⁺ + 2) 432 (44%, M ⁺ + 4) 357 (40%, M ⁺ - 2Cl)
3g	390	3230 (NH)	7.08–7.61 (8H, m, Ar-H)	171.2 (CO)	517 (38%, M ⁺)
		1650 (CO)	8.24 (2H, s, NH, D ₂ O ex.)		519 (100%, M ⁺ + 2) 521 (89%, M ⁺ + 4) 437 (25%, M ⁺ - Br)
3h	420	3240 (NH)	2.42 (6H, s, 2CH ₃)	17.6 (CH ₃)	387 (100%, M ⁺)
		1650 (CO)	7.01–7.18 (8H, m, Ar-H) 8.32 (2H, s, NH, D ₂ O ex.)	172.5 (CO)	389 (33%, M ⁺ + 2) 351 (35%, M ⁺ - HCl)
3i	400	3240 (NH)	3.88 (6H, s, 2OCH ₃)	55.7 (OCH ₃)	419 (83%, M ⁺)
		1660 (CO)	6.87–7.09 (8H, m, Ar-H) 8.32 (2H, s, NH, D ₂ O ex.)	172.8 (CO)	421 (49%, M ⁺ + 2) 418 (50%, M ⁺ - 1)

spectrum of all the synthesized benzoquinone derivatives exhibits a broad band at 390 nm, which is characteristic of dichloro 1,4-benzoquinones (Table 3). IR absorption band at 1640–1660 cm⁻¹ gives the values indication of presence of (C=O) group in the compounds and the band at 3230–3242 cm⁻¹ confirms the presence of (N-H) linkage in the synthesized substituted *p*-benzoquinone **3a-i**. In ¹H NMR, δ values at 6.8–7.7 and 8.30 are due to aromatic and NH (D₂O exchangeable) protons, respectively. Singlet appearing at δ 2.28 and 3.87 are due to methyl and methoxy protons, respectively. In ¹³C NMR, δ values at 172 are due to C=O group. Similarly, signals at 17.6 and 55.7 are observed due to methyl and methoxy carbon atoms. Mass spectra of all the synthesized compounds exhibit molecular ion peak (M⁺) and isotopic abundance peak (M⁺ + 2 and M⁺ + 4) at corresponding *m/z* values which are in accordance with molecular weight of the compounds.

Conclusion :

Highly substituted bioactive, 2,5-diaryl-amino-3,6-dichloro-1,4-benzoquinones **3a-i**, have been synthesized on the solid support of silica gel by the condensation of monosubstituted aryl amines **1a-i** and 3,4,5,6-tetrachloro-1,4-benzoquinones **2** under microwave irradiations. The reaction time has been reduced from 6 h to 45–90 s furnishing upto 87–94% yield. Use of silica gel as solid support has excluded the need of excess organic solvents and external bases, keeping the environment ecofriendly.

Experimental

Reagent-grade chemicals were used without further purification. Anhydrous silica gel 60 (0.063–0.2 mm) was used as solid support after dehydration under microwave irradiation (800 W) for 4 min. Microwave reactions were carried out in LG Microwave oven, Model No. LG MS-194W (2450 MHz, 800 W), UV/Visible spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Lambda 15 UV/Vis spectro-

photometer. FT-IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer (Spectrum RX1) spectrometer using KBr pellets. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer (300 MHz) in DMSO-*d*₆ with tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. Elemental analyses were performed using Elementar Vario EL III Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer. Mass spectra were recorded at room temperature on a Joel SX-102/DA-600 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The reactions inside the microwave oven were carried out in the cycles of 10 s irradiation followed by 30 s rest and each reaction was carried out 5 times to ensure the reproducibility. Temperature of the reaction mixture was measured through Eutech IR Non-Contact Handheld thermometer (-18 to 260 °C) with LASER sighting, Model No. 35625-10. Melting points were determined on a Thomas Hoover melting-point apparatus and are reported uncorrected. UV/Vis maxima, λ_{max}, are given in nm, chemical shifts, δ, for ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR, are given in ppm, relative to internal reference, TMS and IR frequency, ν, in cm⁻¹. The purity of the compounds were checked on aluminum plates coated with silica gel (Merck).

General procedure for the synthesis of 2,5-diarylamino-3,6-dichloro-1,4-benzoquinones (3a-i) :

Conventional method (solution phase) : To a stirred suspension of 0.01 mol chloranil (**2**) and 0.01 mol anhydrous sodium acetate in 100 ml ethanol was added alcoholic solution of 0.02 mol monosubstituted aryl amines (**1a-i**). The mixture was refluxed for the specified time as mentioned in Table 1. After the completion of reaction as monitored by TLC, the refluxed mixture was hot filtered and the residue was washed with hot water and finally with 30% ethanol to give the desired products. Products were recrystallised from DMF/benzene to give 2,5-diarylamino-3,6-dichloro-1,4-benzoquinones (**3a-i**).

Microwave method (solid phase) : A mixture of 2 mmol monosubstituted anilines (**1a-i**) and 1 mmol chloranil (**2**) were solved in 5 ml of EtOH at room temperature and the solution was adsorbed in anhydrous microwave transparent silica gel solid support (5 g) in a small beaker. The mixture was dried in air and kept in alumina bath in the microwave oven followed by irradiations for the specific time (Table 1) intermittently. After the completion of the reaction as monitored by TLC, whole of the reaction mixture was treated with hot-water. The reaction product was extracted with dimethylformamide (DMF); the extract was filtered, dried and then the solvent was removed.

The product (**3a-i**) was first washed with petroleum ether (40–60 °C) and then recrystallised from DMF/benzene.

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